

An Evidence-Based Palliative Care Educational Workshop

Ricky Nguyen Phan, DNP, ACNP-BC, RN, CCRN, TCRN -- Jill Berg, PhD, RN -- Penny Weismuller, DrPH, RN

Background

- Palliative care (PC) focuses on patient's comfort associated with treatments and care of chronic diseases; goals-of-care (GOC) communication; patient-/caregivers-centered care and support.
- Studies found that 92% of patients in the intensive care unit (ICU) did not receive PC within 48 hours of admission, and 72% of those patients died without receiving comfort care.
- Lack of PC education and communication training can be barriers for critical care nurses (CCNs) to engage in GOC conversations and advocate for primary PC delivery.

Purpose

- To develop an evidence-based PC educational workshop to teach CCNs in community hospitals about PC, how to conduct the GOC conversation by using the Serious Illness Conversation Guide (SICG), and the commonly used PC screening tools.

Workshop Development

- Two-hour workshop based on PC literature - integrated active teaching and learning methods.
- Focused on conversation training to assess patients/caregivers understanding of their illness, GOC, and needs for PC.
- Key instruments were introduced (SICG, PC screening tools) & Roleplay was included for interactive practice.
- Content of the workshop-reviewed by five PC experts - then modified and presented to four CCNs.

Donabedian Framework

Workshop Pilot Results

Confidence Level in Goals-of-Care Conversation

Educational Workshop Evaluation From Participants

Discussion

- Five expert reviewers and four CCNs found workshop content helpful - formative evaluation vital.
- Suggested changes included involvement of other PC professionals, such as social workers, and chaplain.
- Two-hour workshop enables implementation at community hospitals - optimizes educational objectives.
- Roleplay was considered a valuable aspect of the workshop regarding difficult conversation.

Nursing Practice Implications

- CCNs should initiate GOC conversation in the ICU to assess patients/caregivers' GOC wishes.
- CCNs need to identify unique needs of patients regarding PC, and GOC.
- CCNs should always be proactive in seeking learning opportunities, practicing PC delivery, and using SICG to initiate GOC conversation at their workplaces.

Conclusion

- This project addressed the needs for palliative care education and goals-of-care conversation training for CCNs in community hospitals and will be further evaluated before dissemination.
References upon request
nphan1@csu.fullerton.edu